

Use of enrichment in broilers

Pixabay

Introduction

Broiler chickens retain behavioural motivations derived from the behavioural repertoire of their ancestor (the Jungle Fowl), including exploration, foraging, dust bathing, and the use of elevated structures for resting (Evans et al., 2023). However, genetic selection programmes aimed at rapid growth have altered the ability to express these behaviours, mainly due to increased body weight, altered body conformation, and reduced locomotor capacity (Riber & Wurtz, 2024). Standardised housing environments, designed to maximise genetic potential and control health risks, further limit the expression of natural behaviours such as exploration, perching, and dust bathing, thereby compromising animal welfare (Guinebretière et al., 2025).

Environmental enrichments are provided to animals with the aim of promoting their welfare, in particular to:

- increase the frequency and diversity of normal and species-specific behaviours;
- prevent the development of abnormal behaviours or reduce their occurrence and complexity;
- promote a positive use of the environment, for example by encouraging access to and use of outdoor areas;
- improve the animals' ability to cope with both behavioural and physiological challenges (Newberry, 1995; Riber et al., 2018).

These objectives can be achieved through various types of environmental enrichment:

- **Social enrichment**, which includes direct or indirect contact (visual, olfactory, auditory) with conspecifics (other individuals of the same species) or with humans.
- **Occupational enrichment**, which encompasses both psychological enrichment (e.g. devices that provide animals with control or challenges) and enrichment that encourages physical exercise.
- **Physical enrichment**, which may involve modifying the size or complexity of the animal's housing environment, or adding elements such as substrates, perches, panels, and barriers.
- **Sensory enrichment**, which involves visual stimuli (e.g. television or video), auditory stimuli (music, vocalisations), or stimuli in other modalities (e.g. olfactory, tactile, gustatory).
- **Nutritional enrichment**, which consists of providing varied or novel food items, or modifying the method of feed delivery. (Bloomsmith et al., 1991)

The aim of this factsheet is to provide practical support for the assessment of environmental enrichment in broilers for verifying whether the housing environment provides adequate resources to promote species-specific behaviours, a more positive use of space, and potentially improved welfare outcomes.

Potentially effective environmental enrichments for broiler chickens include **elevated resting structures, panels, barriers, and straw bales**, as well as **covered verandas and outdoor ranges** (Riber et al., 2018).

Use of enrichment in broilers

Elevated resting structures

Domestic poultry is highly motivated to perch or rest on elevated structures, a behaviour that is probably linked to a predator-avoidance strategy (Malchow et al., 2019). The absence, insufficiency, or inadequacy of elevated elements may cause frustration, as it limits the availability of three-dimensional resting structures, and may also promote competition among animals (EFSA, 2023). Perches and elevated platforms can therefore satisfy broilers' motivation to rest in an elevated position. However, their actual use depends on several factors, including stocking density, structural design, ease of access, and the physical ability of broilers to reach them (Riber et al., 2018). Platforms are used more than perches by both fast-growing and slower-growing broilers; moreover, the presence of ramps with a maximum inclination of 25° facilitates access and use (EFSA, 2023).

Figure 1: Platform

The common practice indicated by EURCAW-Poultry provides for elevated surfaces equal to at least 1% of the poultry house area, giving as an example platform of approximately 3 × 0.70 m and an indicative ratio of 0.3 m² per 1000 chickens. Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/464, which lays down certain rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2018/848 on organic production, instead defines mandatory minimum requirements, namely 5 cm of perch per bird or 25 cm² of elevated resting area per bird. The RSPCA Welfare Standards for Chickens indicate that, for every 1,000 birds, a minimum of 2 m of perch space must be provided. EFSA, from an animal welfare improvement perspective, indicates that the availability of an elevated area (platform) equal to at least 10% of the floor area may help reduce problems related to resting and restrictions on movement. Therefore, since the sources refer to different criteria — a management practice, a minimum regulatory requirement, and a recommendation aimed at improving animal welfare — and since definitive evidence on optimal sizing is lacking, it is not possible to indicate a single precise value that is universally applicable.

Panels and barriers

Vertical panels and perchable barriers can be considered structural enrichments that increase environmental complexity and influence the spatial distribution and behaviour of broilers (Jacobs et al., 2023). They may also provide quiet resting areas against which birds can lie with reduced disturbance (Riber et al., 2018). Barriers differ from panels in that they are generally lower but wider than panels (Riber et al., 2018), thereby allowing the animals to perch on top of them (Jacobs et al., 2023; Riber et al., 2018).

Straw bales

Bales represent a form of environmental enrichment commonly used in commercial broiler production systems and can fulfil several behavioural and structural functions. When intact, they can provide an elevated resting area, offer shelter, help structure the space, and increase opportunities to express exploratory, foraging, and dust-bathing behaviours (Jacobs et al., 2023; Riber et al., 2018). However, their physical characteristics may influence their use: highly compressed bales or bales kept tied with string or plastic film may be difficult to manipulate, especially for younger broilers, thereby reducing the stimulus for exploration (Jacobs et al., 2023). Bales may also pose a potential biosecurity risk, as they could introduce external pathogens. This risk can be mitigated by using disinfected materials, such as treated wood-shaving bales or packaged alternatives; however, as already indicated, these solutions may reduce their effectiveness as enrichment.

Use of enrichment in broilers

According to the RSPCA welfare standards for meat chickens of 24 September 2025, at least 1.5 standard-sized, long-chopped straw bales must be provided for every 1,000 birds. The European Chicken Commitment (ECC), on the other hand, requires the provision of two types of pecking substrates, including straw bales among them. In this case, a minimum density of 1 bale per 1,000 birds is indicated, or preferably 1 bale per 17 m².

Covered verandas

As provided for by Regulation (EU) 2018/848 on organic production, a covered veranda is an outdoor area attached to the poultry house, covered but not thermally insulated, and generally delimited by mesh or wire fencing on one or more sides. In this space, environmental conditions reflect the external climate; the veranda has natural lighting and, where necessary, artificial lighting, and flooring covered with litter. It is accessible to the animals through openings known as popholes, arranged along the long side of the building (EFSA, 2023). The main function of the veranda is to promote behaviours such as foraging, exploration, and dust bathing, as well as to provide additional space and allow the animals to choose between different light conditions, such as natural or solar light, and different temperature conditions (Riber et al., 2018).

To make the veranda more attractive and encourage its use, EFSA 2023 recommends ensuring access from 14 days of age for at least 8 hours per day; providing at least one long side that is open and delimited by mesh or grating, to allow natural light to enter; designing access openings with a maximum height of 25 cm and equipping them with ramps; and providing environmental enrichments, such as straw or alfalfa bales and materials for pecking and foraging (EFSA, 2023).

Figure 3: Covered veranda

Outdoor ranges

Access to an outdoor range gives broilers greater opportunities to express natural behaviours, such as foraging, exploration, dust bathing, and exposure to sunlight, thereby contributing to the fulfilment of their behavioural needs (EFSA, 2023). For these benefits to be effectively achieved, the outdoor area must be appropriately designed and attractive to the animals. Access should be provided from 21 days of age, or even earlier if the openings allow younger birds to enter and exit easily (EFSA, 2023). Slow-growing chickens generally tend to make greater use of the outdoor area, although benefits are also recognised for fast-growing birds (EFSA, 2023). It is also important to ensure easy access through suitable openings and to provide a covered veranda, or a similar structure, as a transition zone.

This can help encourage use of the outdoor area, reduce disturbance and frustration when access is limited, and mitigate the effects of wind and rain (EFSA, 2023). The area should have adequate and well-distributed vegetation cover, amounting to at least 70% of the surface area, of which at least 50% should consist of trees and shrubs, in order to provide shelter and protection and promote natural behaviours (EFSA, 2023). Where such cover cannot be achieved, alternative artificial structures should be provided, together with foraging and pecking materials distributed evenly throughout the area, considering that dense vegetation is particularly important under high-temperature conditions (EFSA, 2023).

Figure 4: Outdoor range

Use of enrichment in broilers

Indications for the assessment of enrichment use in broiler farms differ among different sources indicating a clear gap of knowledge in this area. The EURCAW-Poultry centre adapted selected criteria from the Welfare Quality® protocol to provide some practical indications for assessing the adequacy of enrichments provided.

Assessment of point-source enrichments

Availability of environmental enrichments

[Adapted from Welfare Quality® 2019– Laying hens]

Check the area **inside** and **outside** the house to assess the presence of environmental enrichments.

The following are considered enrichments:

- manipulable materials;
- straw bales;
- panels;
- elevated structures;
- other elements that increase environmental complexity.

The amount of enrichment refers to the number of different **types of enrichment** present: for example, 10 straw bales count as one type of enrichment; similarly, 10 platforms also count as one type of enrichment.

	no enrichment available
	1 or 2 types of enrichment
	3 or more types of enrichment

Use of enrichments [Adapted from Welfare Quality® 2019– Laying hens]

Assess whether the animals use the environmental enrichments by observing the occurrence of the following behaviours:

- **Use of elevated structures for resting:** birds resting on platforms, perches, bales, or other raised structures.
- **Resting near structural elements:** birds resting close to panels, barriers, or straw bales.
- **Dust bathing:** a sequence of behaviours in which a bird, while lying down, shows vertical wing shaking, head rubbing, bill-raking, and scratching with one leg.
- **Preening:** moving the beak through or over the plumage.

- **Foraging:** pecking or scratching the litter while standing.

	None of these behaviours observed
	Up to 10% of the observed animals perform one or more of these behaviours
	More than 10% of the observed animals perform one or more of these behaviours

Assessment of complex environments

Covered veranda

Assess the **use** of the **covered veranda** [Adapted from Welfare Quality® 2019– Laying hens]

Estimate the percentage of veranda occupied by the birds.

	No birds occupy the covered veranda
	Less than 50% of the covered veranda is occupied by the birds
	Between 50% and 100% of the covered veranda is occupied by the birds

Free range

Assess the use of the outdoor area [Adapted from Welfare Quality 2019– Laying hens]

Indirectly assess whether the area is being used by evaluating its condition: check for the presence of droppings, destruction of vegetation cover, and evidence of dust-bathing sites.

Use of enrichment in broilers

	No access to range or no visual effect on the range (= no broiler droppings and plant cover destruction)
	minor effect on the free range or limited to the vicinity of the house (=broiler droppings, destruction of plant cover around the hen house up to 7 m away from entrances to the free range)
	Obvious effect on the range (=broiler droppings, destruction of plant cover found around the house and more than 7 m away from entrances to the free range, natural dust-baths are present)

Assessment of the **presence of shelter** [Adapted from *Welfare Quality® 2019 – Laying hens*]

During the assessment, examine the outdoor range and estimate the percentage of the area covered by vegetation or artificial shelters.

According to the EFSA, 2023, the outdoor area should ensure adequate natural cover, with at least 50% of the surface occupied by tall vegetation, such as bushes and trees, and 70% overall covered by green vegetation adapted to the climatic conditions of the region. Where this level of vegetation cover cannot be achieved due to climatic conditions, suitable structures providing shelter should be installed.

Examples of natural cover:

- tall grass;
- trees;
- maize;
- bushes.

Examples of artificial cover:

- tents;
- roofs;
- elevated camouflage nets.

Closed poultry houses are not considered valid cover.

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